

Solubility effect of CH₃CHO and its mediated electrochemical oxidation in micellar composite solution: An electro-reactor study

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Abstract: We investigated the composite of sodiumdodecyl sulfate (SDS) and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) in 4M H₂SO₄ micellar solution effect on solubility of CH₃CHO. Also, the elimination of acetaldehyde using electrogenerated Co(III) was studied in presence and absence of CTAB via mediated electrocatalytic incineration process. An increased absorption efficiency of CH₃CHO during scrubbing favors more solubility of CH₃CHO in CTAB micellar sulfuric acid solution. The removal efficiency of CH₃CHO shows higher in pure H₂SO₄ solution than in CTAB micellar solution. At the same time, the CTAB micellar contained Co(II) solution shows almost zero oxidation efficiency, which directly relates the removal efficiency of CH₃CHO. Lowering of Co(III) oxidation suggests the complex formation with surfactant or surfactant get degraded. Square wave voltammetry results well correlates with the electro-incineration process in micellar composite solution.

1. Introduction

Electro-incineration is the frontier field in elimination of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) concerned, because electrons provide a versatile, efficient, cost-effective, easily automatizable, and clean reagent [1]. Nowadays, electrochemical technologies have reached a promising state of development and can be effectively used for disinfection and purification of wastewater polluted with organic compounds [2-5]. Since mediated electrocatalytic oxidation (MEO) started, metallic redox couples, such as Ag(II), Ce(IV), Co(III), Fe(III), and Mn(III), or strong oxidizing chemicals, such as active chlorine, ozone, hydrogen peroxide,

persulfate, percarbonate, and perphosphate have been used. For total organics oxidation, a redox pair with a high oxidation potential, such as Ag(I/II) ($E^0 = 1.98V$), Co(II/III) ($E^0 = 1.82V$), or Ce(III/IV) ($E^0 = 1.44V$), have been chosen. Co(III) is a powerful oxidant similar to Ag(II), but with some advantages over the latter, including the fact that cobalt chloride is soluble and, hence, does not precipitate. Cobalt is cheaper than silver, and, under appropriate conditions, it can operate in a divided or undivided cell. Working in the divided cell with HNO₃ as electrolyte, Co(III)-mediated electrochemical oxidation was employed for the destruction of aniline [6] and many chlorinated hydrocarbons [7,8] with over 90% current efficiency. Even the electro-incineration is working well with suitable mediators; the serious problem on elimination of VOCs is its solubility in aqueous medium.

It is well documented that surfactants containing composite solution have many domestic, industrial and environmental applications [9,10]. The effects of individual surfactant on contaminant solubility have been the subject of extensive studies and the enhanced solubility due to monomeric and micellar surfactant aggregates are well defined [11-14]. When hydrophobic VOCs are to be removed from industrial exhaust gases, an absorption reactor filled with pure water is not efficient due to the low solubility of hydrophobic VOCs in water. Surfactants composed of a hydrophilic head group and a hydrophobic tail can be well solubilized in water forming a micelle. The hydrophilic groups are headed to water while the hydrophobic tails aggregates in the middle of the micelle. As hydrophobic VOCs are captured in the hydrophobic tails due to the hydrophobic interaction, their

solubility in the surfactant solution is much larger than that in pure water. Hence, an absorption reactor filled with the surfactant solution is more efficient than one with pure water [15]. Several studies have addressed the effects of surfactants on the apparent Henry's law constants (H^*) of VOCs by the equilibrium tests in closed systems [16-20]. These studies indicated that the presence of surfactants significantly altered equilibrium vapor-liquid partitioning, resulting in substantial reductions in H^* ; indirectly solubility becomes higher. Simply, Solubility of perchloroethylene in surfactants was identified by its conductivity change [21]. With these literature evidence, the present work focuses the solubility effect CH_3CHO and its elimination in SDS, CTAB and Co(II) containing composite micellar solution. Also, because of no studies were reported, to our thorough literature knowledge, in electro-incineration process using this composite micellar solution approach.

In this preliminary study, CH_3CHO was used as model VOC, due to its toxicity to environment [22]. First, the solubility effect of CH_3CHO in SDS and CTAB containing composite solution was studied and compared with pure electrolyte solution. The experimental parameters such as mediator (Co(II)) oxidation efficiency and gas/liquid contact ratio were studied in both composite and pure electrolyte solutions. Finally, the CH_3CHO elimination was checked in composite solution of CTAB and Co(II). Square wave voltammetry experiment was carried out to support the composite solution effect on elimination of CH_3CHO process.

2. Experimental.

Cobalt (II) sulphate (Junsei Chemical Co. Ltd., Japan), sulfuric acid (DC Chemicals Co Ltd, Korea), SDS and CTAB(Sigma Aldrich, USA) were used as received. All aqueous solutions were made by reverse osmosis purified water (Human Power III plus, Korea). Nafion[®] 324 type membrane was obtained from DuPont, USA. PVDF Raschig rings of 1 or 2cm were made in the laboratory for scrubber column. The overall experimental setup that includes electrochemical cell and scrubbing column which is used in this study as of presented in our previous work [23]. One of air pollutant, acetaldehyde was supplied from gas cylinder through an oil free air-compressor (model: AC-B15PA2, Kyungwon Airboy Co. Ltd, Korea) via mass flow controller

(MFC, model: 1179A13CS1BK-S, MKS Co. Ltd., USA), where controlled the both air and CH_3CHO . The homogenized gas mixture (50ppm) was introduced at the bottom of the scrubber and the scrubbing solution of 4M H_2SO_4 containing Co(II)/(III) redox ions was pumped at the top of the scrubber bed through a conical tube at air/solution contact ratio between 2.5 to 12.5.

The active Co(III) was continuously generated at anode (Pt mesh, 140cm^2) in a thin layer flow through divided electrochemical cell. 4M H_2SO_4 was used as electrolyte in both the anodic and cathodic compartment (Ti mesh cathode, 140cm^2), which was circulated from respective storage tanks using magnetic pumps (Pan World Co., Ltd, Taiwan). The anolyte tank was interconnected with scrubbing column to facilitate pollutant/catalyst contact at a given contact ratio. A variable current source (Korea Switching Instrument) was used to generate Co(III) by electrolysis at a constant current of 10A.

All experimental data were collected using a constant concentration of Co(II) (0.01M) unless otherwise mentioned. The cobalt ion concentration in the scrubber solution, was taken as the initial Co(II) concentration, i.e. 0.01M. The oxidation efficiency of cobalt(III) was determined by titration with FeSO_4 and ORP measurements. An online FTIR gas analyzer (I1804 MIDAC Corp., USA) was used to measure the concentration of CH_3CHO . Gas removal efficiencies were calculated from differences of the inlet and outlet concentrations of CH_3CHO shown by FTIR analyzer. Square wave voltammetry was carried out using a BAS-Epsilon EC instrument (USA). Platinum (2mm) and Pt wire served as the working and counter electrodes, and Ag/AgCl served as the reference electrode. All experiments were conducted at room temperature ($25^\circ\text{C} \pm 2$) and atmospheric pressure.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Composite solution effect on CH_3CHO solubility

The solubility of CH_3CHO in the form of outlet concentration from the scrubber column, the electrochemical cell was not in operation during this test, was checked by online FTIR analyzer and is strongly varied in presence of the both surfactants SDS and CTAB, as shown in Fig.1. When SDS was added to the 4M H_2SO_4 solution, the outlet

concentration of CH_3CHO is started increased (Fig.1 respective data) and then reached a steady state at 2h, as similar of only 4M H_2SO_4 solution, which shows directly the less solubility in SDS micellar composite solution. Even, the taken concentration of SDS is higher than its critical micellar concentration (CMC) [24].

Fig.1. Effect of absorption of CH_3CHO with time in different media(indicated in the figure). Conditions: CH_3CHO /liquid contact ratio = 2.5; Pt as Anode.

At the same time, there observed nearly 55% absorption efficiency of CH_3CHO in presence of 25mM CTAB surfactant (Fig.1 respective data), clearly indicates the solubility of CH_3CHO in CTAB micellar composite solution. The higher solubility of CH_3CHO in CTAB micellar solution believes that a little electronegative nature of CH_3CHO , i.e., slightly electro-negativity of CH_3CHO try to solubilized in palisade layer, which very near to the electropositive surface of the CTAB micelle due to electrostatic attraction. In the case of SDS, the solubility trend is reverse due to the electronegative repulsion between negative micellar surface and CH_3CHO at palisade layer.

3.2 MEO at electro-reactor process on effect of composite solution

Fig.2 shows the removal efficiency of CH_3CHO with three different acetaldehyde-liquid contact ratios. The acetaldehyde removal efficiency is almost 100% at low gas/liquid contact ratio in only 4M H_2SO_4 and

it decreases with increasing gas/liquid contact ratio to 80%.

Fig.2. Variation in removal efficiency with different CH_3CHO /liquid contact ratio: (■) without CTAB; (▲) with 25mM CTAB. Conditions: Electrolyte 4M H_2SO_4 .

In presence of the CTAB surfactant, there observed 90% removal efficiency of acetaldehyde at low gas/liquid contact ratio and decreases sharply to 25% with increasing gas/liquid contact ratio. In general, a decrease in removal efficiency with increasing gas-liquid contact ratio is due to not enough concentration of catalyst, here Co(III), with target gases, here acetaldehyde. In the case of CTAB contained micellar solution shows sharp decrease in removal efficiency doubts on two factors. One possibility is, change in cobalt (III) concentration and another one is, CTAB structural change. Note that the color of the Co(III) in 4M H_2SO_4 is blue but, the color becomes orange if CTAB added, which indicates the some complex formation between Co(III) and CTAB. In order to know, the oxidation efficiency was carried out in presence of CTAB micellar solution.

3.3 Effect of oxidation efficiency of Co(II) in composite solution

Figure 3 shows the comparative oxidation efficiency of 0.01M Co(II) without CTAB and with CTAB(25mM), which were obtained by electro-reactor at given experimental conditions(10A, three different gas/liquid contact ratio). The conversion

efficiency of Co(II) is 60% at low gas-liquid contact ratio and decreases to 40% at 12.5 gas-liquid contact ratio.

Fig.3. Effect of cobalt (II) oxidation efficiency with various Gas-liquid contact ratios in 4M H₂SO₄: (■) without CTAB; (▲) with 25mM CTAB. Conditions are same as in Fig.2.

In the case of 25mM CTAB composite solution, the oxidation efficiency is almost zero at all studied gas-liquid contact ratios. This clearly indicates that a stable complex is formed between Co(III) and CTAB, which makes it difficult to calculate the oxidation efficiency of Co(III). Also, the oxidation efficiency of Co(III) is well correlated with the removal efficiency of acetaldehyde. In order to confirm further, the square wave voltammetry studies were carried out in two different solutions and the results are depicted in Fig.4. The square wave voltammetry response shows two oxidation processes: one is around 0.01V, which is for Co(II)/Co(0) redox process and another one is for Co(III)/Co(II) (1.85V) redox process. In the absence of CTAB, there is observed a huge Co(III) oxidation current above 1.85V (no well defined oxidation peak due to oxygen evolution region). But, completely minimized oxidation current in the presence of CTAB evidences some complex formation. Also, one peak at 1.0V becomes predominant, which confirms the complex formation, because of the stability of Co(III) brought its oxidation to 1.0V.

Fig.4. Square wave voltammogram of 50ppm CH₃CHO at Pt electrode in 4M H₂SO₄, Scan rate = 50 mV s⁻¹.

Conclusions: The CTAB and Co(II) micellar composite solution effectively solubilized the air pollutant acetaldehyde. The electrochemically oxidized Co(III) in CTAB micellar solution facilitates the complex formation between each other. Reduced elimination efficiency of acetaldehyde confirms the inactiveness of Co(III) due to complex formation with CTAB. Again, evidence through square wave voltammetry results that the electro-oxidation of CH₃CHO in CTAB micellar composite solution is less prominent, even though it is solubilized well in the same. Further studies are focused towards the possibility of CTAB destruction in the presence of Co(III) mediator.

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